

DYES DERIVED FROM ACETONE DICARBOXYLIC ACID

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Acetone dicarboxylic acid has been condensed with resorcinol at 200°. A red crystalline dye (dye I) is obtained which gives a red colour with greenish fluorescence when dissolved in alkali.

A study of the constitution of dye I has been made. A new dye (dye II) has been obtained from 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid and resorcinol, and its constitution assigned. The octa- and hexabromo compounds of dyes I and II respectively have also been prepared and studied.

Acetone dicarboxylic acid was condensed with resorcinol by Pechmann (*Annalen*, 1894, 261, 166) using concentrated sulphuric acid as condensing agent to yield 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid.

Later Limaye and Bhawe (this *Journal*, 1931, 8, 137) obtained β -arylglutaconic acids by condensing acetone dicarboxylic acids with phenol using sulphuric acid as a condensing agent at a low temperature.

Dixit *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1945, 23, 207) obtained a dilactone of $\beta\beta$ -di-(2:4-dihydroxyphenyl)glutaric acid using phosphorus pentoxide or anhydrous aluminium chloride as the condensing agent when acetone dicarboxylic acid was condensed with resorcinol; Dixit and Mulay (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 14) obtained β -arylglutaconic acid with sulphuryl chloride as a condensing agent.

In the present investigation, acetone dicarboxylic acid was condensed with resorcinol at a high temperature (180°-200°) using a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid as the condensing agent. In spite of partial decomposition of the former the product (m. p. 210°) was obtained in good yield. (This resorcinolacetone dicarboxylein will be known hereafter as dye I). Dye I did not react with phenylhydrazine, hydroxylamine etc. indicating the absence of a free carbonyl group.

To understand the mechanism of this condensation, 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid, which might be the first product formed, was condensed with resorcinol, but a different compound was obtained which gave a red colour with blue fluorescence when dissolved in alkali. It melted at 179° [this resorcinol- β -(2:4-dihydroxyphenyl)glutaconein will be known hereafter as dye II].

On bromination dye II gave a hexabromo compound. It was supposed that the double bond did not get brominated as on bromination of phenylglutaconein only four atoms of bromine entered the molecule and not six.

The analytical data and the above observation clearly indicate that the dye II has the structure I(X-H):

Also the bromo compound of the dye II has been shown to have the structure (I, X=Br).

The formation of the dye II was further confirmed by condensing β -(2:4-dihydroxyphenyl)glutaconic acid (Dixit and Mulay, *loc. cit.*) with resorcinol when a dye, identical with dye II, was obtained. Mixed melting point of the two dyes showed no depression.

To elucidate the structure of dye I, the dilactone of $\beta\beta$ -di-(2:4-dihydroxyphenyl)glutaric acid was condensed with resorcinol at 180° . The product was a mixture, but the pure dye (m. p. 210°) could be obtained, which was found to be identical with dye I (mixed m. p. with dye I). Also the brominated compound of this dye gave the same melting point as the octabromo compound of dye I and showed no depression when their mixed melting point was determined. Dye I on bromination took up eight atoms of bromine, thus, clearly indicating the presence of four aromatic nuclei in dye I. The structure thus assigned to dye I is:

The following formula is assigned to the brominated dye I:

The reaction proceeds probably as follows :

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Acetone dicarboxylic acid was prepared in the manner as described in "Organic Syntheses" (Coll. Vol. I).

Resorcinol-acetone Dicarboxylein.—An intimate mixture of pure acetone dicarboxylic acid (15 g.) and resorcinol (45 g.) was heated in an oil-bath to 140°, 4 to 5 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid were then added when a vigorous reaction took place which subsided in 20 to 30 minutes. The temperature was then raised to 200° and the mixture heated for ten hours. On cooling the hard brittle mass was dissolved in a very dilute caustic soda solution, stirred mechanically and to it dilute hydrochloric acid added cautiously. While adding the acid a tarry mass appeared which was removed by filtration before further addition of the acid (if on further addition of the acid a black tarry mass again appears it is to be removed before finally acidifying it). A red dye was obtained which was purified by again dissolving it in caustic soda and precipitating with dilute hydrochloric acid. It was finally purified by dissolving it in dilute alcohol (65% to 70) and diluting with water till a red crystalline dye appeared which was filtered. (The filtrate still contained a mixture of dyes from which the pure dye could not be isolated). It was recrystallised from dilute alcohol. It is a red crystalline substance and gives a beautiful red colour when dissolved in alcohol and a greenish fluorescence on the addition of alkali, m. p. 210°, yield 6 g. (pure). (Found : C, 70.0 ; H, 4.24. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 70.10 ; H, 4.03 per cent).

Resorcinol-acetone Dicarboxylein from the Dilactone of $\beta\beta$ -di-(2 : 4-dihydroxyphenyl)glutaric Acid.—A mixture of the dilactone (5 g.) and resorcinol (3.5 g.) was heated in an oil bath with a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid at 180° for 6 hours. It was cooled and extracted with a dilute caustic soda solution and precipitated with dilute HCl. The red dye was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol till a crystalline substance melting at 210° was obtained, yield 0.5 g.

Octabromoresorcinol-acetone Dicarboxylein.—The pure dye (1.2 g.) was dissolved in alcohol or glacial acetic acid and 1 c. c. of bromine slowly added. (If glacial acetic acid is used, a solution of bromine in it is taken). Soon the crystalline dye separated and it was filtered off, washed first with dilute alcohol and then with water. It was further purified by recrystallisation from alcohol and dried under vacuum, m. p. 190°, yield 1.8 g. (Found : Br, 56.30. $C_{22}H_{12}O_8Br_8$ requires Br, 56.70 per cent).

Resorcinol- β -(2 : 4-dihydroxyphenyl)glutaconein.—Pure 7-hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (5 g.) was intimately mixed with resorcinol (5 g.) and heated in an oil-bath at 170° for about half an hour and then a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid were added. A vigorous reaction took place and after the reaction had subsided the temperature was raised to 200°. After heating for about 6 hours it was cooled. The hard mass was extracted with several portions of very dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline solution was stirred mechanically and dilute hydrochloric acid added very slowly till the solution became acid to litmus. A red dye mixed with some tarry matter was obtained. It was filtered and the crude dye was once more dissolved in dilute caustic soda and reprecipitated cautiously with dilute hydrochloric acid. It was further purified by dissolving in alcohol and diluting the alcoholic solution with water. The dye so obtained was sufficiently pure. Its crystals are red and dissolve in alcohol giving a red colour and a blue fluorescence when alkali is added to it, m. p. 179°, yield : 2 g. (pure dye). (Found : C, 68.30; H, 4.50. $C_{23}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 68.30; H, 4.00 per cent).

Resorcinol- β -(2:4-dihydroxyphenyl)-glutaconein from β -(2 : 4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-glutaconic Acid.—An intimate mixture of the acid and resorcinol (2 g. each) was heated in an oil-bath with a few drops of sulphuric acid at 200° for about 6 hours. It was extracted with dilute caustic soda solution and precipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid and finally recrystallised from alcohol, m. p. 179°, yield 1 g.

Hexabromoresorcinol- β -(2 : 4-dihydroxyphenyl)-glutaconein.—To the pure resorcinol dye (1 g.), dissolved in the minimum quantity of alcohol, bromine (1.2 c. c.) was added slowly. It was allowed to cool and a few drops of water were added to facilitate the separation of the compound. It was filtered and washed first with very dilute alcohol and then with water till the filtrate was free from bromine. The dye was dried under vacuum. It was purified by recrystallising from alcohol as a dark red crystalline substance, m. p. 243°, yield 1.5 g. It dissolves in alcohol giving a deep red solution, the colour of which is intensified by the addition of alkali. (Found : Br, 54.10. $C_{23}H_{10}O_7Br_6$ requires Br, 54.60 per cent).

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